

Research

A study on the effects of Foreign Direct Investments on Cambodia's Economic Growth

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Abstract: Foreign direct investment plays a key role in improving development, economic growth, and global integration. The importance of FDI provides benefits to countries with economic growth through increased national income, the creation of new jobs, higher wages, experience, greater exports, skilled management, and increased productivity through new technologies. In this way, FDI becomes the objective for developing countries to absorb the capital inflow and many new technologies to improve their economy through their policies to attract more and more foreign direct investment. Cambodia undertakes a new policy of identical treatment for absorbing all investors both local and overseas. The new law helped enhance increasing investment projects and gave a wider opportunity for foreign investors to get benefits from their investment in the Kingdom. This paper attempts to analyze the effects of foreign direct investment and its importance on the economic growth of Cambodia. The study uses time-series data from 1995 to 2018. The study uses a correlation matrix and multiple regression analysis techniques to analyze the data. Data access was done in the Excel program, which could be converted into STATA/SE 12.0. The data has been obtained from the World Development Indicators (WDI) database published by the World Bank and the Ministry of Labor and Vocational Training of Cambodia. The result revealed that FDI has positive effects on the economic growth of Cambodia, and most importantly, the employment opportunities were created for the domestic population, which in the long term helps unemployment and poverty reduction. Finally, the study recommends that to attract more and more FDI, the government should bring reforms in the domestic market, keep strong macroeconomic and political stability, and develop human capital resources in the country.

Keywords: Effects, Foreign Direct Investment (FDI), Economic Growth, Cambodia

1. Introduction

Nowadays is the term of Globalization, which reflects the free movement of multinational companies (MNCs) from developed to developing countries in the world. According to the development and the economic changes around the world, many countries lack the investors that can lead to new incentives for local and regional development. Most of the transition countries have been giving out the transition from communism and the central planning to open economy has gone through structural and dramatic changes. A huge amount of FDI is regarded to flow into developing countries through Multinational corporations (MNCs) or multinational enterprises (MNEs). All the countries have set all the possible policies to attract more and more FDI via removing restrictions of foreign investment, regulations, promoting domestic economic policies, enhancing financial sector development and encouraging environments for foreign investment. FDI represents an important source of new financial sources that will support local economies, particularly in developing countries. Not every country can attract neither FDI nor every investor risks their investment without studying the local conditions in the host country, it is necessary to understand the motivations of foreign investors. Cambodia is the developing country among ASEAN members state and she was challenged with the civil war for decades, the economy rate was slow down, all types of infrastructure and human resources were destroyed; therefore, it is quite challenging for the country to stand up and strive to develop her economy with empty hands. For an instant, Foreign Direct Investment flows into Cambodia were significantly increased since the 1990s. Cambodia undertakes a new policy of identical treatment for absorbing all investors both local and abroad. The new law helped enhance increasing investment projects and gave a wider opportunity for foreign investors to get benefits from their investment in Cambodia. Therefore, the government makes the policies for foreign investors more confident to promote economic growth in this small state. These policies include fiscal policy exemption from taxes, monetary policy dealing with the exchange rate, inflation, interest rate, etc. Regulatory policies related to entry, ownership, export, and repatriation, privatization and other relevant policies. Therefore, we can say that through these inflows of FDI, investors manipulate limited productive resources of the host country though it has great positive effects, however, they are least as compared with the negative ones. Nevertheless, its effects appeal varies from country to country. Therefore, this paper uses time-series data from 1995 to 2018 by using correlation matrix and

multiple regression analysis techniques to analyze the data, and answer to the question: Does foreign direct investment stimulate economic growth of Cambodia?

The remainder of the paper proceeds as follows: section 2 illustrates the literature review, section 3 focuses on an overview Cambodian economy and the role of government policies to promote FDI, Section 4 Methodology and Data analysis with the findings, Section 5 provides the conclusion and recommendations of the study.

2. Literature Review

According to (World Investment, 2017) Foreign direct investment (FDI) is defined as “an investment that implies a long-term relationship and reflects a long-term interest and control on the part of an entity resident in an economy (foreign direct investor or parent company) in a company resident in an economy different from foreign direct investor (FDI enterprise or foreign subsidiary)”. FDI is an investment made by a company or individual in a country with commercial interests in another country, either through the establishment of commercial operations or the acquisition of commercial assets in the other country, such as ownership or control participation in the foreign company¹. While Economic growth is defined as an increase in the capacity of an economy to produce goods and services, compared from one time to another². The direct capital financing of FDI can benefit the host country through technology, human capital formation, creation of the competitive business environment, development of enterprise and integration of international trade. Therefore, many emerging economies have liberalized their FDI regime and formulated FDI favorable policies. At the macro level, FDI extremely contributes to higher GDP per capita, industrial productivity (Honglin, Zhao Zhongxiu and Zhang Kevin, 2010), and higher encouraging productivity externalities. (Wang, 2010) Capital flows and technology transfer are considered accelerators of economic growth, foreign direct investment (FDI) will promote the economic growth of the host country. Moreover, (Zhang, 2001) noticed that FDI tends to stimulate economic development while the host economy implements an opened trade policy, improves education and preserves macroeconomic stability. (M.E.Hussain & M.Haque, 2016) studied an empirical analysis of the relationship between foreign direct investments, trade, and growth rate of GDP per capita in Bangladesh by using time series data from 1973-2014, and the result reveals

¹ Investopedia dictionary, FDI

² Investopedia dictionary, Economic Growth

that trade and foreign investment variables have a significant impact on the GDP growth rate per capita. Along with (Dritsakia, Chaido, and Emmanouil Stiakakisb, 2014), FDI rises export capacity in the recipient country and results in growing profits in the foreign exchange market, mainly in developing countries. Through (Wang, et al, 2009) FDI promotes the economic growth of a host country through different channels but the most important channels are technology. Technology transfer can be taken place in the host country through multinational firms while spillovers could happen through the interaction of multinational firms with domestic firms, suppliers, customers, and the workforce. Therefore, FDI can have positive effects on income (Gao, 2004). FDI has a direct effect on local and regional economic growth because they contribute to capital accumulation and enable know-how and technology transfer to the host country. Because of the changes and economic developments throughout the world, many countries leftover investments that could generate new incentives for local and regional development. In addition to a direct effect of FDI on economic growth, FDI boosts economic growth indirectly. The direct technology transfer enlarges the stock of knowledge in the host country through labor training and skill achievement, new management performs, and organizational arrangements (De Mello, 1999). Although, there are no accord effects on FDI on the economic growth of the host country the number of studies that show the positive effects of FDI is much higher than those which focus on the negative effects (Vissak, Tiia, and Tõnu Roolah, 2005). The existing literature showed the effects of foreign direct investment on the economic growth of a developing country particularly Cambodia. Additionally, it also revealed the channels through which FDI contributes extensively to a country's economic growth. Among ASEAN countries' economies, (Bhatt, 2014) examines the effects of FDI on economic growth. The empirical results of the study verify strongly support the connecting effect of FDI on growth for the countries under consideration. Moreover, the same empirical results are also confirmed by other studies of (Vogiatzoglou, K and Phuong NTN, 2016) and (Tan, et al, 2016). An additional current study also mentions the important role of FDI in motivating economic growth in the Eurozone countries (Pegkas, 2015). In 2002, the Organization of Economic Cooperation (OECD) reported the fact that FDI is considered as the only source of economic growth and modernization for the countries with weak economies. (Lee, et al, 2004) Indicated that FDI is the most useful way to achieve economic growth. Most of the authors consider FDI as an important driver of economic development in a host country. Moreover (Athukorala, Prema-chandra, and Hal Christopher Hill, 2000) emphasized the fact that foreign

direct investment plays a positive role in the economic growth of the host country through the transfer of capital, technology and management resources. In addition, they affirm that these resources have the potential to accelerate the economic growth of the host country and most notably, these resources can be moved only to the host country through FDI. Through (Borensztein et al, 1998) tested the effect of FDI on economic growth in a cross country regression framework, utilizing data on FDI flows from industrial countries to 69 developing countries from 1970 to 1989. Their results suggested that FDI is an important vehicle for technology transfer and contributes relatively more to growth than domestic investment. However, the higher productivity of FDI holds only when the host country has a minimum entrance stock of human capital. Also (Har, et al, 2008) studied the relationship between economic growth and FDI in Malaysia and the result FDI is a good source of economic growth. Besides capital, FDI brings several benefits into the host country like employment, management resources, modern technology, and competitive goods. However, some empirical studies do not support the growth impact of FDI. For instance, (Žilinské, 2010) states that the effects of foreign direct investment can be positive as well as negative. Greenfield FDI has more positive effects than mergers acquisitions or sometimes has negative externalities on the economic growth of the host country. So, the impact of foreign direct investment on the economic growth of the host country is still contentious. Nevertheless, a recent study has increasingly revealed an endogenous long-run impact of FDI in economic growth determination. Through the neoclassical models, FDI can only affect growth in the short run because of diminishing returns of capital in the long-run (Anderson, et al, 2014). A large number of studies have been conducted so far to find out the effects of FDI on the economy but there is no consensus. Some studies came up with the findings that FDI has positive effects on the economy while others with negative effects. Some studies have found that the effects of FDI depend on the absorptive capacity of the host country that includes the political, economic and technological conditions of the host country.

3. Overview of Cambodian Economy and the role of government to promote FDI

The Kingdom of Cambodia is located in the southern part of Southeast Asia's Indochina Peninsula. The country covers an area of 181,035 km² with a population exceeds 16 million and shares a border with Thailand, Vietnam, and Laos. Cambodia's southeastern border lies along the Gulf of Thailand. To attract more and more FDI, Cambodia had to make important economic reform,

moving from a centrally planned economy to a market-oriented economy in the late 1980s at that time the country also improves investment and business environments for foreign investors by establishing the Investment Law in 1994. According to the Council for the Development of Cambodia (CDC), in 1995, one year after the enactment of the Law on Investment, the investment amount approved by the CDC totaled some 2.3 billion dollars. In 2008, approved investment has been increased to 10.89 billion US dollar in which agriculture sector is attracting up to 106.73 million US dollar, while tourism and services sector are reaching up to 8.77 billion US dollar and 1.29 billion US dollar remarkably. The Cambodian economy has grown frequently from a state of extreme poverty in the early 1990s. Cambodia also has unexpectedly experienced of highest inflation 15 percent in 1991-1993, 10.3 percent in 1998, and decreased to 5.6 percent in 2007, and 3 percent in 2018. In 1993, Cambodia had national elections and mistrust and printing of money to finance the budget deficit. Similarly, in 1997/1998, in time of the Asian financial crises and national elections, the government borrowed money from banks to finance the deficit, making more money circulating in the market and caused inflation. Both external and internal factors cause high inflation in 2007 and 2008. The external shocks were accredited to rise in oil price from 22\$ a barrel in 2003 to 120\$ in March 2007, the rise in the price of imported goods and the exchange rate (the depreciation of dollars and the appreciation of euros) and the increase in global demand for resources, especially from China and India. The Cambodian economy experienced rapid growth with an average of 7.6 percent per annum between 1993 and 2003 and continued to achieve high growth of more than 10 percent per year between 2004 and 2007. Due to the global financial crisis of 2009, the trends were fallen from 6.7 percent in 2008 to 0.1 percent in 2009. However, the trend has been returned in 2010 with 5.9 percent to the robust growth of 7 percent per year until 2018. Strong economic performance is broad-base on tourism, garment export, construction, and real estate, and agriculture sectors rising at robust rates. Similarly, GDP per capita over the last two decades is steadily rising with the maximum value of US\$ 1512.13 in 2018, which means the economic growth of Cambodia has been increasing for this time. Furthermore, in July 2016, the World Bank officially reviewed the state of Cambodia's economy, moving from "low income" to "lower-middle-income". The measure is based on Cambodia's estimated gross national income (GNI) per capita. Low-income economies are those with a GNI per capita of less than \$ 1,025, while low-middle-income countries are those between \$ 1,026 and \$ 4,035. While the change reflects an improved economy, it can eventually lead to a reduction in foreign aid and preferential

access to trade³. Three main sectors play an important role in the economic development of Cambodia, such as agriculture, industry and the services sector. In 2018, the services sector is the largest contributor to GDP, accounting for 39.49 percent of total GDP, followed by industry at

Source: WB, last updated date 02 October 2019

32.29 percent, agriculture 20.01 percent, and other at 6.21 percent.

Foreign direct investment inflows to Cambodia have grown powerfully in recent years due to strong macroeconomic policies, political stability, uphold economic growth in the region and an open investment market; reaching US\$ 3.1 billion in 2018 (Figure 2), 11.51% increase compared to the previous year. However, according to (ASEAN Investment Report, 2018) noticed that FDI in Cambodia is growing in finance and other services, and increased in real estate investments. Nowadays, China is the biggest investment in Cambodia (the biggest sources of FDI), followed by Hong Kong, the United States, and the Netherlands.

Four industries accounted for 80 percent of their inflows in 2017. Finances, services, and other real estate have dominated, and production remains the main recipient, despite a decline of 16

³ Cam McGrath and Hor Kimsay. *Cambodia's economic status raised to lower-middle income*. July 25, 2016. Accessed October 01, 2019 from: <http://www.phnompenhpost.com/business/cambodias-economic-status-raised-lower-middle-income>

percent (ASEAN Investment Report, 2018). The manufacturing industry absorbed 12 percent of investment in Cambodia. Normally, the industry was the biggest recipient, dominated by investment actions in garment production. FDI in services in Cambodia continued to increase, maintained by strong investment activities in finance, real estate, and other services. The entrance of more foreign banks led to an increase in FDI in banking and finance, as well as the

Source: WB, last updated date 02 October 2019

Government's decision to raise the minimum capital requirements of the banks. The strong economic development also led to an increase in investment in real estate development, counting with industrial estates. Likewise, many digital and internet services companies are also investing in Cambodia because of the rise in smartphone consumptions, internet usages, and tourism activities.

However, Cambodia has attracted a large amount of foreign investment in the country, as it has provided many opportunities for companies seeking new developing countries to invest. **Political Stability** and **Macroeconomic stability** is the key for any investors to invest in the host country, if the country is not stable on political no one investor goes to invest in that country, also have a low trade deficit and low budget deficit which are the parts of macroeconomic possibility. Cambodia has also offered confidence to foreign investors through its recent political stability and the improvement of the legal system, that is, the introduction of the Anti-Corruption Law. For the moment, the next general election in 2018 will be in a more peaceful, quiet and better than in previous times, from the current ruling party (Cambodian People's Party – CPP) is expected to

keep its winning because of its strong supporters; for instance, election in 2018, CPP already win 125 seats over 125 seats (or equal to 100 percent majority, while 50 percent +1 vote is full enough to perform a new government). On the other hand, Cambodia has low inflation.

The **inflation** in Cambodia is relatively low at about 3 to 5 percent annual. The exchange rate is stable 4000 KHR per 1\$ which helps the investors have more and more confidence to invest in Cambodia. For example, if they put today 1\$ you get 4000KHR next week they get 5000KHR or 2000KHR it is very hard for them to do the business.

Open Economy, Cambodia has transformed herself into an open economy since the early 1990s and has improved year-by-year on the level of economic liberty. According to the Index of Economic Freedom in 2019, ranked Cambodia with a score of 57.8 points, making its economy ranked 105th freest of the world⁴, 22 among 43 countries in the Asia-Pacific region and much higher than other countries with emerging markets.

Preferential Access to ASEAN and the World: Thanks to the Paris Peace Accord in 1993 and open market policy from the Royal government, Cambodia is able to join and become a member of various international and regional organizations that facilitate trade, which in turn the country can enjoy special trading status on duty-free privileges for exports and Most Favored Nation (MFN) treatment. These organizations include, among others, the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN), the World Trade Organization (WTO) and the ASEAN-China Free Trade Area (ACFTA). Cambodia also possesses other beneficial agreements such as ASEAN-China Comprehensive Economic Cooperation Agreement, ASEAN-Japan Comprehensive Economic Partnership, Agreement on Comprehensive Economic Cooperation ASEAN-Korea and a dozen other multilateral agreements with developed countries, including the USA (Generalized System of Preferences - GSP) and the European nations (Politics Everything but Arms). Through these regional integrations and agreements, all investors have enjoyed the greatest opportunity to spread billions of clients with preferential admission.

Attractive Investment Incentives: Cambodia has adopted several laws and regulations to progress its open economy and encourage foreign investment. Presently, Cambodia offers investors one of the most liberal investments regime and tax incentive schemes in Southeast Asia. The country offers a fast-track investment consent process and “**One-Stop-Service**” (only 28 days)

⁴ 2019 Index of Economic Freedom, Cambodia, Accessed October 10, 2019 from: <https://www.heritage.org/index/country/cambodia>

for foreign investors, who can own 100 percent of their business with a long-term lease of up to 99 years of land. Furthermore, prices of products and services depend on market price, which reflects that business owners have greater control of company operations and flexibility on their price strategy. Therefore, it implies that Cambodia has a large liberal investment regime. Recently, Cambodia has introduced Special Economic Zones (SEZs), which bring together all industrial activities. For now, the Cambodian law has offered wonderful tax incentives to investors, since they can enjoy a tax exemption on business profits for up to 8 years; full of duty-free tariffs for raw materials, machinery, equipment, without export taxes and value-added tax (for SEZs). Moreover, Cambodia also allows foreign investors to employ foreigners up to 10 percent of the total workforce if the experience is needed to do business, and provides a permanent visa for the families of the investors, as well as the free repatriation of profits. Though, all FDI projects must be registered with the Development Council of Cambodia (CDC) to qualify, called “Qualified Investment Projects (QIP)”, and be eligible to receive commercial incentives.

Low labor cost: is another reason to invest in Cambodia, where the total labor force has more than 8.8 million (or 61 percent) of the total population and the average age is only 23 years. Among the countries with emerging markets in the region, the labor cost of Cambodia is the most interesting for foreign investors who focus on the advantages of costs. It implies that Cambodia has a high potential workforce for foreign companies, as it has a young, hardworking and honest employee with the lowest salary in the region.

4. Methodology and Data

4.1 Research design

Secondary data sources are used to assess the effect of FDI on the economic growth of Cambodia. The study analysis time series data over the period of 1995 to 2018 in the following variables; the GDP of Cambodia (GDP), Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) net inflows, inflation rate (InfR), exchange rate (ExR), interest rate (InR), normal minimum wage of Cambodia garment and footwear worker in US\$ per month (NMW), Labor force participation rate (LbfR), and Unemployment rate (UnemR). Data access was done in the Excel program, which could be converted into STATA/SE 12.0. Data has been obtained from the World Development Indicators (WDI) database published by the World Bank and the Ministry of Labor and Vocational Training of Cambodia.

4.2 Descriptive Statistics

The findings of the study on real GDP, Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) net inflows, inflation rate (InfR), exchange rate (ExR), interest rate (InR), normal minimum wage in US\$ per month (NMW), Labor force participation rate (LbfR), and Unemployment rate (UnemR) are detailed below.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
GDP	24	9.866	6.671	3.120	24.57
FDI	24	1.010	0.965	0.080	3.10
InfR	24	3.715	3.375	(4.283)	12.25
ExR	24	3,843.62	468.98	2,450.83	4,184.92
InR	24	3.327	2.799	1.260	8.80
NMW	24	67.458	39.736	40.00	170
LbfR	24	81.970	1.743	78.600	85.39
UnemR	24	1.615	0.553	1.050	2.55

4.2.1 Real GDP

The findings on the GDP real values are shown in Table 1 indicate the trend of real Gross Domestic Product over the period of 1995-2018. The minimum value of GDP is US\$ 3.12 billion while the maximum value of GDP is calculated as US\$ 24.57 Billion. The standard deviation value is calculated as US\$ 6.67 billion. There is a steady increase in the values of GDP over the past 24 years that means the economic growth of Cambodia has been increasing for the last 24 years.

4.2.2 Foreign Direct Investment (FDI)

The findings on the FDI values are shown in Table 1 indicate the trend of FDI values over the period of 1995-2018. The minimum value is calculated as US\$ 0.08 billion in 2003 while the maximum value is calculated as USD 3.1 billion in 2018. The findings indicate the rising and falling trend in the values of FDI during the last 24 years. The standard deviation value is calculated as 0.96. The greater value of the standard deviation indicates that there is a variation to the annual values of foreign direct investment.

4.2.3 Inflation Rate

The findings on the inflation rate nominal values are shown in Table 1 indicated the trend of annual average inflation rate values over the time of 1995-2018. The minimum value of inflation is

recorded as -4.28 percent in the year 2000 while the maximum value of 12.25 percent in 2008, while the mean is 3.71. The standard deviation value is calculated as 3.37. The findings show that there is a rising and falling trend in the values of the inflation rate with significant annual variations over the last 24 years.

4.2.4 Exchange Rate

The findings on the exchange rate are shown in Table 1 indicate the trend of foreign exchange rate values of Cambodia (Riel) relative to the US\$ from 1995 to 2018. The minimum exchange rate value is calculated as 2450.83 riels in 1995 while the maximum exchange rate value is calculated as 4184.92 riels in the year 2010 after the economic crisis in the world. The findings indicate that there is a rise in the values of the exchange rate over the past period of 24 years.

4.2.5 Interest Rate

The findings on the annual interest rate are shown in Table 1 indicates the trend of annual interest rate values over the period of 1995-2018. The minimum interest rate value is calculated as 1.26% in 2010 and the maximum value is calculated as 8.8 in 1996. The findings indicate fluctuating levels of interest rate values with annual variations over the last 24 years. The findings indicate that there is a rising and falling trend in the values of interest rate over the past 24 years.

4.2.6 Normal minimum wage

The findings on the annual normal minimum wage of Cambodia garment and footwear workers are shown in Table 1 indicates the trend of annual normal minimum wage values over the period of 1995-2018. The normal minimum wage value is calculated as US\$ 40 in 1995 and the maximum value is calculated as US\$ 170 in 2018. There is a steady increase in the values of normal minimum wage values over the last 24 years. The findings indicate that there is a rising trend in the values of the normal minimum wage over the past 24 years.

4.2.7 Labor force participation rate

The findings on the labor force participation rate are shown in Table 1 indicates the trend of annual labor force participation rate values over the period of 1995-2018. The minimum labor force participation rate value is calculated as 78.6 percent in 2000 and the maximum value is calculated as 85.36 in 2010. The findings indicate fluctuating levels of the labor force rate values with annual variations over the last 24 years. The findings indicate that there is a rising and falling trend in the values of labor force participation rate over the past 24 years.

4.2.8 Unemployment rate

The findings on the annual Unemployment rate are shown in Table 1 indicates the trend of annual Unemployment rate values over the period of 1995-2018. The minimum Unemployment rate value is calculated as 1.05 percent in 2018 and the maximum value is calculated as 2.55 percent in 1999. The findings indicate fluctuating levels of Unemployment rate values with annual variations over the last 24 years. The findings indicate that there is a rising and falling trend in the values of the unemployment rate over the past 24 years.

4.3 Correlation Matrix

The correlation matrix in Table 2 below shows that FDI is positively related to Cambodian GDP. The exchange rate, normal minimum wage, and labor force also positively related to Cambodian GDP. But the inflation rate, interest rate, and unemployment rate are negatively related to the GDP of Cambodia.

Table 2: Correlation Matrix

	GDP	FDI	InfR	ExR	InR	NMW	LbfR	UnemR
GDP	1.000							
FDI	0.982	1.000						
InfR	-0.133	-0.154	1.000					
ExR	0.464	0.406	-0.204	1.000				
InR	-0.656	-0.588	0.121	-0.831	1.000			
NMW	0.930	0.898	-0.173	0.322	-0.465	1.000		
LbfR	0.200	0.207	0.139	0.443	-0.607	-0.097	1.000	
UnemR	-0.745	-0.676	0.023	-0.750	0.965	-0.567	-0.605	1.000

4.4 Model Specification

To determine the relationship between foreign direct investment and economic growth in Cambodia, the study conducts multiple regression analyses among the variables. The regression model specification is as follows;

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + \beta_4X_4 + \beta_5X_5 + \beta_6X_6 + \beta_7X_7 + \epsilon$$

Where, Y= Gross Domestic Product (Dependent Variable)

Independent Variables:

X_1 = Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) in Billion US\$

X_2 = Inflation Rate (InfR)

X_3 = Exchange rate (ExR)

X_4 = Interest Rates (InR)

X_5 = Normal Minimum Wage (NMW)

X_6 = Labor force Rate (LbfR)

X_7 = Unemployment Rate (UneR)

β = Independent Variable coefficient, α = the constant, ϵ = the error term

4.5 Multiple Regression Analysis

The study conducts multiple regression analyses to determine the relationship between foreign direct investment and economic growth in Cambodia. The findings of the study are presented in table 3.

Table 3: Model Summary

Model	R	R-square	Adjust R-square	Std. error of the estimate
1.	0.9961	0.9921	0.9886	0.485

The seven independent variables Foreign Direct Investment net inflows, inflation rate, exchange rate, interest rate, normal minimum wage, labor force participation rate, and the unemployment rate was studied, indicate 99.21 percent of the variance in economic growth in Cambodia as represented by R2. It means that other factors not included in this study contribute 0.79 percent of the variance in the dependent variable.

Table 4: ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	Degree of Freedom (df)	Mean Square	F	Significance
Regression	1015.48	7	145.06	286.06	0.000
Residual	8.11	16	0.51		
Total	1023.59	23	44.50		

In Table 4, the findings show that the significance value is less than 0.05, thus the model is statistically significant to predict how FDI, inflation rate, exchange rate, interest rate, normal minimum wage, Labor force participation rate, and Unemployment rate affect the GDP of Cambodia. The F value calculated is greater than the F value critical which shows that the overall model was significant.

Table 5: Regression Analysis

GDP	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P>t	[95% Conf. Interval]	
FDI	4.259	0.485	8.78	0.000	3.231	5.287
InfR	0.038	0.052	0.73	0.475	-0.072	0.148
ExR	0.000	0.001	-0.27	0.788	-0.001	0.001
InR	-0.134	0.303	-0.44	0.663	-0.776	0.508
NMW	0.048	0.014	3.47	0.003	0.019	0.078
LbfR	-0.024	0.181	-0.13	0.895	-0.407	0.359
UnemR	-1.501	1.605	-0.94	0.364	-4.902	1.901
_Cons	7.670	16.550	0.46	0.649	-27.415	42.755

From the regression findings in table 5 above have substituted the values in the regression Equation; $Y = \alpha + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + \beta_4X_4 + \beta_5X_5 + \beta_6X_6 + \beta_7X_7 + \epsilon$ becomes:

$$Y = 7.67 + 4.26X_1 + 0.04X_2 + 0.00X_3 - 0.13X_4 + 0.05X_5 - 0.02X_6 - 1.5X_7 + \epsilon$$

According to the equation, taking all the factors, if FDI net inflows, inflation rate, exchange rate, interest rate, normal minimum wage, labor force participation rate, and unemployment rate constant at Zero, GDP will be 7.67 percent. The findings of the data reveal that a unit increase in foreign direct investment (FDI) will lead to 4.26 percent rises in GDP; a unit increase in inflation rate will result in 0.04 percent increases in GDP; while a unit of exchange rate will decrease at 0.000 percent in GDP, a unit of interest rate will decrease at 0.13 percent in GDP, a unit of normal minimum wage will increase at 0.05 percent in GDP, a unit of labor force will decrease at 0.024 percent in GDP, and a unit of unemployment rate will decrease at 1.5 percent in GDP. At a 5 percent level of significance and 95 percent level of confidence, FDI had a 0.0000 level of significance; the inflation rate had a 0.475 level of significance; the exchange rate had a 0.788 level of significance, interest rate had a 0.663 level of significance, normal minimum wage had a

0.003 level of significance, labor force participation rate had a 0.895 level of significance, and unemployment rate had a 0.364 level of significance.

4.6 Discussions result

The result of this paper revealed that FDI is positively related to GDP growth of Cambodia, and parallel with the outcomes by other researchers on the relationship between FDI and economic growth. As a result of (De Mello, 1999) found that FDI flows have a significant effect on economic growth and it acts as a driving force in the economic growth process. (Anderson et al 2014) came up with the findings that investment is the most important determinant of economic growth as identified by neoclassical and endogenous growth models. Among ASEAN countries' economies, (Bhatt, 2014) examines the impact of FDI on economic growth. Moreover, (Pegkas, 2015) founded the important role of FDI in stimulating economic growth in the Eurozone countries. Also, (Athukorala, Prema-chandra, and Hal Christopher Hill, 2000) emphasized the fact that foreign direct investment plays a positive role in the economic growth of the host country through the transfer of capital, technology and management resources. Nonetheless, (Har, Wai-Mun, Kai-Lin Teo, and Kar-Mun Yee, 2008) studied the relationship between economic growth and FDI in Malaysia and the result FDI is a good source of economic growth. Besides capital, FDI brings several benefits into the host country like employment, management resources, modern technology, and competitive goods. So the finding in this paper reveals that FDI has a positive effect on economic growth both in the short run and long run.

5. Conclusion and recommendations

To conclude, Cambodia is an ASEAN member state, had recognized through many awful political generations, affecting almost complete damage of all of the infrastructure, human resources, and approximately two million innocent lives. To rebuild the economy, foreign capital, mainly FDI is extremely needed as part of capital growth because national capital alone is not sufficient for growth-enhancing in this country. Therefore, the government of Cambodia changed the economy from the centrally planned to the market-oriented system in the late 1980s. Moreover, FDI starts to flow into this country's economy. However, the quantity was still small due to the remaining political instability. After the UN-supervised election in 1993, and the Investment Law had been enacted in 1994, it is perceived that FDI progressively increases. The governments believe that the

variable to be a remarkable contributor to Cambodian economic growth as proposed in theory. The paper aims to analyze the effect of foreign direct investment (FDI) on the economic growth of Cambodia over the period 1995-2018 by using correlation matrix and multiple regression to determine the effects of FDI on the economic growth of Cambodia. The results reveal that FDI has a positive effect on the economic growth of Cambodia in these periods. Also, correlation matrix analysis suggests that FDI and GDP are positively related to each other. Based on the findings, the study recommends that government and policymakers should bring reforms in the domestic market to attract more FDI in Cambodia. Most importantly, to gain more FDI, the government should keep strong macroeconomic policies, enlarge physical infrastructure, eliminate restrictions against inward FDI, enhance the monetary sector progress, and promote more environments for trade and investment. Last but not least, the government should not forget the development of human capital resources because the variable represents the capacity of the economy building. A further vital contributing factor of FDI and growth is political stability. Macroeconomic and political stability must be maintained because it might be the most important supporter to FDI and growth in the country. If there are political instability in the country, it might adversely affect the economy as a whole.

References

- [1] Anderson, Wineaster, Marcellina M. Chijoriga, and John RM Philemon, eds. (2014). *Promoting trade competitiveness in developing countries*. Cambridge Scholars Publishing.
- [2] ASEAN Investment Report. (2018). *Foreign Direct Investment and the Digital Economy in ASEAN*. Jakarta: ASEAN Investment Report.
- [3] Athukorala, Prema-chandra, and Hal Christopher Hill. (2000). FDI and host country development: The East Asian experience. *Economics Division, Research School of Pacific and Asian Studies & Asia Pacific School of Economics and Management, Australian National University*.
- [4] Bhatt, P. R. (2014). Foreign direct investment in ASEAN countries 1990–2012. *Revista Galega de Economía*, 23, 133–144.
- [5] Borensztein et al., (1998). How does foreign direct investment affect economic growth? *Journal of International Economics*, 01(45), 115–135.
- [6] De Mello, L. R. (1999). *Foreign Direct Investment-Led Growth: Evidence from Time Series and Panel Data* (Vol. 51). Oxford economic papers.

- [7] Dritsakia, Chaido, and Emmanouil Stiakakisb. (2014). Foreign Direct Investments, Exports, and Economic Growth in Croatia: A Time Series Analysis. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 181-190.
- [8] Gao, T. (2004). FDI, openness and income. *The Journal of International Trade & Economic Development*, 13(3), 305-323.
- [9] Har, Wai-Mun, Kai-Lin Teo, and Kar-Mun Yee. (2008, April). FDI and economic growth relationship: An empirical study on Malaysia. *International Business Research*, 01(02), 11-18.
- [10] Honglin, Zhao Zhongxiu and Zhang Kevin. (2010, July 16). FDI and industrial productivity in China: Evidence from panel data in 2001–06. *Review of development economics*, 14, 656–665.
- [11] Lee, Minsoo, and Moon Joong Tcha. (2004). The color of money: The effects of foreign direct investment on economic growth in transition economies. *Review of World Economics*, 140(2), 211-229.
- [12] M.E.Hussain & M.Haque. (2016). Foreign Direct Investment, Trade, and Economic Growth: An Empirical Analysis of Bangladesh. *Economies, MDPI, Open Access Journal*, 1-14.
- [13] Pegkas, P. (2015). The impact of FDI on economic growth in Eurozone countries. *The Journal of Economic Asymmetries*, 12, 124–132.
- [14] Tan, Bee Wah, and Chor Foon Tang. (2016). Examining the causal linkages among domestic investment, FDI, trade, interest rate and economic growth in ASEAN-5 countries. *International Journal of Economics and Financial*, 1(6), 214–220.
- [15] Vissak, Tiia, and Tõnu Roolaht. (2005). The negative impact of foreign direct investment on the Estonian economy. *Problems of Economic Transition*, 48, 43-66.
- [16] Vogiatzoglou, K and Phuong NTN. (2016). Economic openness and economic growth: A cointegration analysis for ASEAN-5 countries. *The European Journal of Applied Economics*, 13, 10–20.
- [17] Wang, Miao, and M. C. Sunny Wong. (2009). *What Drives Economic Growth? The Case of Cross-border M&A and Greenfield FDI Activities* (Vol. 62). Kyklos: 316-330.
- [18] Wang, Y. (2010). FDI and productivity growth: the role of inter-industry linkages. *Canadian Journal of Economics/Revue canadienne d'économique*, 43(4), 1243–1272.
- [19] World Investment. (2017). *METHODOLOGICAL Note*. World Investment Report. Retrieved October 01, 2019, from https://unctad.org/en/PublicationChapters/wir2017chMethodNote_en.pdf

- [20] Zhang, K. H. (2001). Does Foreign Direct Investment Promote Economic Growth? Evidence from East Asia and Latin America. *Contemporary Economic Policy*, 175–185.
- [21] Žilinskė, A. (2010). NEGATIVE AND POSITIVE EFFECTS OF FOREIGN DIRECT INVESTMENT. *Economics & Management*.

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